

Assessment of Difficult Chemistry Concepts among Teachers and Students in Colleges of Education in North West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study conducted in Colleges of Education, North West, Nigeria assessed teachers' and students' perceptions of difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program. The study was guided by five objectives, five research questions and five hypotheses tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of confidence. Two validated questionnaires, the "Chemistry Teachers Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire" (CTIODCQ) and the "Chemistry Students Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire" (CSIODCQ) were used to collect data from 68 chemistry teachers (48 males 20 females) and 335 chemistry students (156 males and 179 females) in three conventional Federal Colleges of Education in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. The samples were drawn using multistage sampling technique from a total population of 82 chemistry teachers (58 males and 24 females) and 2071 students (964 males and 1107 females). The CTIODCQ and CSIODCQ had Cronbach reliability coefficient 0.71 and 0.74 respectively. The analysis was done using IBM-SPSS version 26.0, employing statistical methods such as mean, standard deviation, t-test, and ANOVA. The findings revealed that teachers generally found the 20-item chemistry concepts to be moderately difficult, with no significant difference in their responses ($F(2,1037) = 1.845$; $p > 0.05$). However, students perceived these concepts as difficult, with a significant difference in their perceptions ($F(2, 6196) = 13.321$; $p < 0.05$). There was no statistically significant distinction between male and female teachers' or students' perceptions of concept difficulty. The study recommended enhancing teacher training, curriculum review, and student-centered pedagogical approaches in Nigerian Colleges of Education to address these challenges.

Keywords: Assessment, Difficult, Chemistry, Concepts

Introduction

As a nation, Nigeria envisions to be one of the leading economies of the world. As at 2007, the country had a lofty goal of being one of the 20 most developed economy by the year 2020 which had come and gone. The vision was popularly christened vision 2020 (Inegbenebor, *et al.*, 2018). The industrialization desire of Nigeria has however not abated. Be that as it may, it is common knowledge however, that the secret of any nation's development lies in the stock and quality of her science and technological know-how. Anaeto, *et al.*, (2016), succinctly captured the fact, "Science and Technology hold the key to the progress and development of any nation. Technology plays a fundamental role in wealth creation, improvement of the quality of life and real economic growth and transformation in any society" (p.1).

Quality Science and Technology Education should be rooted on strong foundation at the basic level of education. The need to have quality education at that level demands that among others, skilled teachers of right quality and attitudes should mount the saddle of service delivery at that level. Colleges of Education, the third tripod of the tertiary education in Nigeria are mandated to train sub-degree teachers for the basic education sector (National Policy on Education, 2014). Products of this system are awarded the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), the minimum entry qualification into the teaching profession in Nigeria (National Policy on Education 2014). The Colleges are regulated by the National Commission for Colleges of Education, which also set the minimum academic standard as well as accredit the programs. The minimum curriculum for NCE awarding institution is called the Minimum Standard. The Standard is reviewed after every five years and the current one subsisting is the 2020 edition. Teaching science as an integrated whole and the need to produce specialist teachers had engendered the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) to undertake far reaching reforms to reposition Colleges of Education to deliver on its mandate so as to produce teachers of requisite stock and quality for the

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basic education level. Many Colleges of Education are hosted in the North West region of Nigeria, comprising seven states: Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Jigawa, Sokoto and Zamfara.

The central place of chemistry discipline in science as well as its import in national development had been expressed in grandiose terms (Muoneke *et al.*, 2021). Some regard it as a central science while others opined it is the mother of all science owing to its confluence and influence. Furthermore, chemistry education is rate as the gate way to the deliverables of national development and growth occasioned via science education enterprise. Chemistry is prided as having features that makes it such a fascinating and engaging subject to teach and these also contribute to it being a challenging subject for many learners (Taber, 2019). Many concepts in chemistry are important for learning and understanding how the world functions in daily life (Haruna, 2016). There is hardly any science discipline at the tertiary level that a credit pass in chemistry at the O'level is not a prerequisite for admission. This underscores the need for proper grasp of the subject at the foundation level. Sadly, literature of teachers and students' conceptual difficulties in chemistry abounds (Cleopas, *et al.*, 2023; Adum-Gyamfi & Asaki, 2023; Essiam, *et al.*, 2023; Oladejo, *et al.*, 2023; Obikezie, *et al.*, 2023; Anim-Eduful, & Adu-Gyamfi, 2022; Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022; Saadon & Abbood, 2022; Stroumpouli & Tsaparlis, 2022; Akaygum & Arkun, 2022; He, *et al.*, 2021; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021; Nartey & Hanson, 2021; Nkiko, 2021; Longyil & Agbo, 2020; Awaah, *et al.*, 2020; Montenegro & Cascolan, 2020; Kenni, 2020; Amoke 2020; Moyo, 2018; Jack, *et al.*, 2017; Jack *et al* 2017; Agogo & Onda, 2014; Otor & Achor 2013; Edu, *et al.*, 2012). Analysis of available literatures showed that learners conceptual difficulties could be due to teachers related factors (Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki, 2023; Onu, *et al.*, 2022; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021; Nartey & Hanson, 2021; Kinyanjui, 2019; Weiss, 2019; Atuahene, 2019; Kretschmann, 2015) and learners related factors (Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2015; Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2014) among others. When learners are unable to develop an appropriate structure of chemistry concepts, conceptual difficulties which ultimately results in poor academic performance arises. Given the pervasive influence of chemistry, understanding of its concepts is imperative to producing the critical mass of science teachers and scientists needed to drive sustainable national development goal.

Teachers, owing to their expertise and requisite classroom experience, can offer valuable insights into challenging specific concepts, their teaching difficulties, and the learning gaps observed among students (Nwagbo, *et al.*, 2021). Students equally, through their individual learning experiences, can pinpoint specific concepts they find difficult and the factors underpinning these difficulties (Afolabi, *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, understanding the perceptions of teachers and students regarding difficult chemistry concepts in this context is crucial for enhancing pedagogical practices and curriculum development. By exploring these perceptions, educators can gain valuable insights into the underlying factors influencing the teaching and learning of challenging chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program, a course which is central to science and science related fields.

Statement of the Research Problem

Chemistry is a fundamental science subject crucial for various science fields. However, students often struggle with the subject, leading to poor performance. In Nigeria, the Chief Examiners report on the West African Senior School Certificate Examination have consistently highlighted that students struggle with some chemistry concepts (Obikezie, *et al.*, 2023; Anim-Eduful, & Adu-Gyamfi, 2022; Kenni, 2020; Amoke 2020). Consequently, research efforts had been devoted to perceived difficult chemistry concepts. Studies span across difficult primary science concepts (Edu, *et al.*, 2012), secondary school chemistry (Oladejo, *et al.*, 2023; Nwagbo, *et al.*, 2021; Kyado, *et al.*, 2021) and undergraduate chemistry (Stroumpouli & Tsaparlis 2022; Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022; Awaah, *et al.*, 2020; Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2015). But research on conceptual difficulties in Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) chemistry curriculum in general and the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in particular has not received attention as evidenced by the paucity or no literature on such study. This research intends to fill that gap. The NCE program is crucial to training teacher manpower for the basic level of education. This study which aims at assessing the chemistry concepts pre-service teachers (students) and in-service teachers (lecturers) in Colleges of Education within North West, Nigeria, consider challenging is apt as its findings are vital to improving chemistry education and preparing quality future teachers for effective service delivery.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this research are to:

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1. Identify chemistry concepts teachers in Colleges of Education perceive to be difficult to teach in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program;
2. Identify chemistry concepts students in Colleges of Education perceive to be difficult to learn in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program;
3. Identify factors responsible for the teachers perceived conceptual difficulty in chemistry concepts;
4. Identify factors responsible for the students perceived conceptual difficulty in chemistry;
5. Determine gender difference on the teachers and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program.

Research Questions

The questions posited to guide this study are:

1. Are there concepts teachers in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?
2. Are there concepts students in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?
3. What are the factors responsible for the teachers' perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts?
4. What are the factors responsible for the students' perceived conceptual difficulty?
5. Do gender difference affect the teachers' and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program in colleges of Education?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

1. HO₁: Teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult;
2. HO₂: Students in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult;
3. HO₃: Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of education;
4. HO₄: Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education;
5. HO₅: Gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted to assess difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard among teachers and students in colleges of education in North West, Nigeria. The target population for this study was 82 (58 males and 24 females), the total number of chemistry teachers and 2071 (964 males and 1107 females) the total number of chemistry students in the Federal Colleges of Education in the North-West, Nigeria. There are a total of five Federal Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria (National Commission for Colleges of Education, 2021). They are: Federal College of Education (T), Bichi, Federal College of Education (T), Gusau, Federal College of Education, Kano, Federal College of Education Katsina and Federal College of Education, Zaria. These Colleges are categorized into two types: conventional and Technical. The Conventional Colleges are three while the Technical are two. The Colleges were purposively used for the study because they have same source of funding and extant administrative documents. The three conventional Colleges (Federal College of Education, Kano, Katsina and Zaria) were randomly sampled for the study. A total 68 chemistry teachers and 335 chemistry students constitute the sample size (Israel, 1992).

Two research questionnaires, Chemistry Teachers Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire (CTIDCQ) and Chemistry Students Identification of Difficult Concepts Questionnaire (CSIDCQ) were designed by the researchers for the study. The questionnaires have three sections A, B and C. Section A deals with the biodata of the respondents. Section B, containing 20 five Likert scale rating items, deals with chemistry concepts perceived too difficult to teach or learn in the 2020 NCE Minimum standard. The Likert scale range from 1 to 5, very difficult (5), difficult (4), Undecided (3), Moderately Difficult (2) and not difficult (1). For section C equally containing 20 five point Likert scale items deals reasons why teachers and students perceive the chemistry concepts in the 2020 NCE Minimum Standard Difficulty to teach or learn. The responses range from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), strongly disagree (1).

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The decision rule for section B was 1-1.49 not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. While for section C, 1-1.49 strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly agree. Two experts, one in Science Education and the other Chemistry validated the instruments for the study and the suggestions/ observations raised were effected on the instrument appropriately. After pilot testing, Split-half method was used in order to determine the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach was used to determine the coefficient values of 0.71 for the teachers' instrument and 0.74 for the students' instrument; thus the instruments were adequate for the study. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0.

Results

Research Question 1

Are there concepts teachers in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?

Table 1: Summary of teachers in colleges of education response on chemistry concepts perceived difficult in 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Dual nature of matter	68	2.19	1.37	MD
2	Nature of Ionic Crystals	68	2.27	1.25	MD
3	Dipole Moment and Bond Character	68	2.25	1.36	MD
4	Redox Reaction (balancing of redox reaction/predicting products at electrode)	68	2.08	1.37	MD
5	Polarization and Quantum mechanics	68	2.19	1.22	MD
6	Quantum number and Quantum mechanics	68	2.85	1.47	D
7	Stoichiometry and the mole concept	68	2.12	1.29	MD
8	Isomerism	68	1.33	0.76	ND
9	Carbonyl Compounds (Reaction mechanisms in organic chemistry), qualitative organic analysis or Functional group detection	68	1.92	1.23	MD
10	IUPAC nomenclature of organic compounds	68	1.4	0.82	ND
11	Hybridization	68	1.9	1.07	MD
12	Symmetry and Chirality	68	2.38	1.21	MD
13	Chemical Kinetics (first order and second order reactions)	68	2.35	1.34	MD
14	Activated complex, intermediate and transition state	68	1.98	1.09	MD
15	Equilibrium and second law of thermodynamics	68	2.29	1.26	MD
16	Heat and Temperature	68	1.61	0.87	MD
17	Phase changes	68	1.85	1.07	MD
18	Colligative Properties	68	1.83	1.02	MD
19	Partial molar quantities	68	2.37	1.1	MD
20	Real and Ideal Solutions	68	1.9	1.16	MD

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Cumulative mean & Standard deviation

2.05

1.17

MD

Data source: Field survey 2023

MD means moderately difficult and ND not difficult. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. From the cumulative mean value of 2.05 which is within the range 1.50 -2.49, the teachers overall perceived the concepts to be moderately difficult.

Research Question 2

Are there concepts students in colleges of Education perceive to be difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program?

Table 2: Summary of students in colleges of education response on chemistry concepts perceived difficult in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Dual Nature of Matter	335	2.24	1.62	MD
2	Nature of Ionic Crystals	335	2.56	1.51	D
3	Dipole Moments and bond Character	335	2.83	1.47	D
4	Redox Reactions(balancing of redox reaction / predicting product at electrodes)	335	2.84	1.59	D
5	Polarization and Polarizability	335	2.95	1.45	D
6	Quantum numbers and Quantum Mechanics	335	2.81	1.58	D
7	Stoichiometry and the mole concept	335	3.02	1.39	D
8	Isomerism	335	2.32	1.54	MD
9	Carbonyl compounds (Reaction mechanisms in organic chemistry) qualitative organic analysis or functional group detection	335	2.77	1.59	D
10	IUPAC nomenclature of organic compounds	335	2.15	1.50	MD
11	Hybridization	335	2.47	1.51	MD
12	Symmetry and Chirality	335	3.23	1.37	D
13	Chemical Kinetics (first order and second order reactions)	335	2.65	1.64	D
14	Activated complex, intermediate and transition state	335	3.03	1.54	D
15	Equilibrium and second law of thermodynamics	335	2.91	1.61	D
16	Heat and Temperature	335	2.45	1.55	MD
17	Phase Changes	335	2.85	1.35	D
18	Colligative properties	335	3.01	1.35	D

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19	Partial molar quantities	335	2.90	1.36	D
20	Real and Ideal Solutions	335	2.55	1.54	D
Cumulative mean & Standard deviation			2.73	1.50	
					D

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: MD means moderately difficult and D means difficult. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies not difficult, 1.50 -2.49 moderately Difficult, 2.50 -3.49 difficult, 3.50 – 5.00 very difficult. From the cumulative of 2.73 which is within the range 2.50 -3.49, it implies the students generally perceived the chemistry concepts difficult to learn.

Research Question 3

What are the factors responsible for the teachers' perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts?

Table 3: Summary of teachers' response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of mentoring by senior colleagues	68	3.17	1.46	A
2	Lack of Collaboration and team teaching	68	3.33	1.35	A
3	Lack of post lecture review by a team of lesson observers	68	3.50	1.35	SA
4	Chemistry is complex and the concepts abstract	68	3.10	1.33	A
5	Teaching Techniques not learner-centered	68	3.33	1.17	A
6	Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich teaching	68	3.02	1.21	A
7	Difficulty in English, the medium of instruction/communication	68	2.87	1.22	A
8	Lack of numeracy skills	68	2.90	1.29	A
9	Overloaded course content	68	3.60	1.35	SA
	Confusing Technical Terms	68	2.65	1.17	
10	Lack of Scientific Reasoning skills	68	3.15	1.29	A
11	Lack of interest and motivation towards teaching chemistry	68	2.90	1.38	A
12	lack of exposure to scientific language	68	2.63	1.25	A
13					A

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14	Weak background in requisite knowledge	68	3.33	1.35	A
15	Not integrating ICT in teaching	68	3.54	1.34	SA
16	Inadequate exposure of teachers to problem solving	68	3.35	1.12	A
17	Lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life application	68	3.71	1.36	SA
18	Unconducive learning environment	68	3.88	1.35	SA
19	Lack of mathematical reasoning skills	68	3.23	1.18	A
20	Lack of higher order cognitive skills (Synthesis, application, evaluation)	68	3.33	1.32	A
Cumulative mean & Standard Deviation			3.23	1.92	A

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: SA means strongly agree and A means agree. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly agree. From the cumulative mean of 3.23 which is within the range 2.50 -3.49, the teachers generally agreed that the itemized factors were responsible for the perceived moderate difficulty of the concepts to teach.

Research Question 4

What are the factors responsible for the students' perceived conceptual difficulty?

Table 4: Summary of students' response on factors responsible for perceived conceptual difficulty

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of mentoring by the lecturers	335	3.31	1.48	A
2	Lack of Collaboration and team learning	335	3.51	1.35	SA
3	No feedback from peers	335	3.27	1.37	A
4	Chemistry is complex and the concepts are abstract	335	3.38	1.39	A
5	Poor teaching techniques	335	3.06	1.50	A
6	Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich learning	335	3.51	1.36	SA
7	Difficulty in English, the medium of instruction/communication	335	3.31	1.41	A
8	Lack of numeracy skills	335	3.48	1.28	A
9	Overloaded course content	335	3.72	1.38	SA
10	Confusing technical terms	335	3.46	1.29	A
11	Students lack of scientific/critical reasoning skills	335	3.47	1.31	A
12	Lack of interest and motivation of students towards chemistry	335	3.34	1.42	A
13	Lack of exposure to scientific language	335	3.43	1.40	A

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14	Students weak background in requisite knowledge	335	3.61	1.30	SA
15	Teachers teaching strategy does not integrate ICT	335	3.06	1.41	A
16	Inadequate exposure of students to problem solving	335	3.36	1.33	A
17	Lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life situation	335	3.44	1.33	A
18	Unconducive learning environment	335	3.22	1.37	A
19	Lack of mathematical reasoning skills	335	3.37	1.33	A
	Students are generally in low order Bloom taxonomy cognitive skills	335	3.26	1.42	
20					A
	Cumulative mean & Standard deviation		3.38	1.37	A

Data source: Field survey 2023

Key: SA means strongly agree and A means agree. Mean range of 1-1.49 implies strongly disagree, 1.50 -2.49 Disagree, 2.50 -3.49 agree and 3.50 – 5.00 strongly agree. From the cumulative mean 3.38 within is within the range 2.50 -3.49 the students equally agreed that the itemized factors were responsible for the perceived difficulty to learning the chemistry concepts.

Research Question 5

Do gender difference affect the teachers' and students perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program in colleges of Education?

Table 5: Summary of mean score of male and female teachers and students perception of difficult chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean difference	decision
Male	204	2.73	1.48	0.01	difference does not exist
Female	199	2.72	1.52		

Data source: Field survey 2023

The mean of the males' perception of difficult chemistry concept is 2.73 while that of the females is 2.72. The difference in their means is 0.01 implying that difference does not exist in their perception of difficult chemistry concepts.

Hypothesis 1

Teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult

Table 6: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of perception of teachers' response on difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5.503	2	2.751	1.845	.159
Within Groups	1546.588	1037	1.491		
Total	1552.091	1039			

Data source: Field survey 2023

$F(2, 1037) = 1.845; p > 0.05$. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis teachers in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult is retained.

Hypothesis 2

Students do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult in colleges of Education

Table 7: Summary of One-Way Analysis of Variance of Students response on Perception of difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p (Sig level)
Between Groups	62.114	2	31.057	13.321	.000
Within Groups	14445.230	6196	2.331		
Total	14507.344	6198			

Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 6196) = 13.321; $p < 0.05$. The $p < 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis students in colleges of Education do not significantly perceive chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of education.

Table 8: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of teachers response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in Chemistry concepts among teachers in Colleges of Education

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p (Sig level)
Between Groups	10.118	2	5.059	2.896	.056
Within Groups	1811.781	1037	1.747		
Total	1821.899	1039			

Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 1037) = 2.896; $p > 0.05$. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among teachers in Colleges of education is not rejected.

Hypothesis 4

Perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education

Table 9: Summary of One-Way ANOVA of Students response on factors responsible for perceived difficulty in Chemistry concepts among students in colleges of Education

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p(Sig level)
Between Groups	22.427	2	11.213	5.905	.003
Within Groups	11768.901	6197	1.899		
Total	11791.328	6199			

Data source: Field survey 2023

F (2, 6197) = 5.905; $p < 0.05$. The $p < 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis perception of the factors responsible for the perceived difficulty in chemistry concepts do not differ significantly among students in Colleges of Education is rejected.

Hypothesis 5

Gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education

Table 10: Summary of t-test score of the Male and Female Teachers and Students on their perception of difficult Chemistry concepts in 2020 Minimum Standard

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p (sig level)	decision
Male	204	2.73	1.48	401	0.04	0.404	not significant
Female	199	2.72	1.52				

Data source: Field survey 2023

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[$t(401) = 0.04$; $p > 0.05$]. The $p > 0.05$ implies that the hypothesis, gender has no significant difference on teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program in Colleges of Education is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result in table 1 showed that the teachers generally perceived the chemistry concepts to be moderately difficult. This finding aligns with that of Cleopas, *et al.*, (2023), Akaygum & Arkun (2022) & He, *et al.*, (2021). Only one concept quantum numbers and quantum mechanics (mean value = 2.85) was considered difficult to teach by the teachers. None of the concepts was perceived to be very difficult and the one-way analysis of variance of teachers' response on perception of difficult chemistry concepts, $F(2,1037) = 1.845$; $p > 0.05$ (Table 6) showed statistically significance difference does not exist in the teachers response. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the teachers' perception of difficult concepts is therefore not rejected. Researchers have ascribed the outcome of teachers' perception of difficult concepts to qualification (Kyado, *et al.*, 2021) and teachers' disposition (Nartey & Hanson, 2021).

The students' responses (as shown in Table 2) indicated that they found the concepts to be challenging. The one-way analysis of variance on students' perceptions of difficult chemistry concepts (Table 7) revealed a significant difference, $F(2,6196) = 13.32$; $p < 0.05$, indicating variations in the students' perceptions. This finding is supported by Longyil & Agbo (2020), Awaah, *et al.*, (2020), Jack *et al* (2017) and Agogo & Onda (2014). It is intriguing that while the teachers generally did not perceive the concepts difficult to teach, the students perceived them difficult to learn. This finding is not unusual (Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, 2014). The students' response could be indicative of pedagogical issues on the part of the teachers (Adum-Gyamfi & Asaki, 2023; Essiam, *et al.*, 2023) or students related factors (Nkiko, 2021; Montenegro & Cascolan, 2020; & Moyo, 2018). On critical analysis of the students' responses, the students perceived the concept of quantum number and quantum mechanics which were general and introductory physical chemistry difficult to learn. The teachers equally found them difficult to teach. These concepts poses challenge to other students (Nitereka, *et al.*, 2022).

On factors responsible for the perceived chemistry concepts difficulty, the cumulative mean of 3.23 (Table 3) shows that the teachers generally agree that the 20 items are factors responsible for their perception of chemistry concepts difficulty. However, five factors each having a mean score of 3.50 and above were strongly agreed by the teachers as responsible factors. The five factors are; lack of post lecture review by team of lesson observers (mean 3.50), Overloaded course content (mean 3.60), not integrating ICT in teaching (mean 3.54), lack of relating chemistry concepts to real life application (mean 3.71) and uncondusive learning environment (mean 3.88). The result from table 6, $F(2,1037) = 2.896$; $p > 0.05$, shows that no significant relationship exists in the teachers' perception of factors responsible for the difficult concepts. Onu, *et al.*, (2022) had reported that integration of ICT in teaching was yet to be popular amongst teachers in Colleges of Education in the North West, Zone of Nigeria. Not integrating ICT in teaching (mean 3.54) by the teachers seems to be an issue of concern (Kinyanjui, 2019; Atuahene, 2019; Kretschmann, 2015). Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki (2023) in their work on factors contributing to teachers' conceptual difficulties in teaching high school organic chemistry identified four factors; tertiary exposure, professional collaboration, professional competence, and pre-tertiary exposure. Tertiary exposure is about the experiences and knowledge an individual teacher had from his or her university education.

Professional collaboration explains how the teachers develop their knowledge in both content and pedagogy through their continual engagement and participation in professional group, sharing experiences and knowledge. Lecture observation by lesson observers with the aim of having post lesson reviews is an integral part of the professional collaboration. So the finding from this study in an aspect is in agreement with that of Adu-Gyamfi and Asaki (2023) and also in line with Garcia and Weiss (2019) who claimed that teachers have limited access to some of the types of professional development that are highly valued and more effective.

The students on their part agreed that the 20 items (Table 4) were factors responsible for their perception of difficult concepts. They equally strongly agreed that four factors stood out: Lack of ollaboration and team learning (mean 3.51), Lack of understanding of online educational resources to enrich learning (mean 3.51), Overloaded course content (mean 3.72) and Students weak background in requisite knowledge (mean 3.61). Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, (2015) underscored weak mathematical background as factor affecting students' conceptual progress in thermodynamics. Though the teachers and students differed on the factors they strongly agreed were responsible for their perception of difficulty they however converged on the factors of overloaded curriculum and lack of collaboration and team work. This result agreed with that of Woldeamanuel, *et al.*, (2014).

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While the no significant difference existed in the teachers' perception of factors responsible for the perceived concept difficulty (Table 9) $F(2,1037) = 2.896$; $p > 0.05$; the students result (table 9), $F(2, 6196) = 13.321$; $p < 0.05$ showed otherwise.

The result from table 5, shows no difference existed in favour of any gender in the gender perception of concept difficulty among teachers and students. The $p > 0.05$ (Table 10) implies that the hypothesis "Gender has no significant difference on the teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard for chemistry program" is accepted. The finding agrees with Oladejo, et al., (2023), Nitereka, *et al.*, (2022), Saadon & Abbood (2022) and Otor & Achor (2013) where weak relationship or no relationship was established between gender and concept difficulty.

Conclusion

Assessment of difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 minimum standard among teachers and students in colleges of education in North West, Nigeria was studied. This study offers valuable insights into how the teachers and students in Colleges of Education in the North West perceived 20-item chemistry concepts drawn from the 2020 Minimum Standard for chemistry program difficult. Generally, the teachers perceived the 20-item chemistry concepts moderately difficult. They equally strongly agreed that five factors accounted for their perceived difficulty. The students on their part perceived the 20-item concepts difficult to learn. On critical analysis of the students' responses, the concepts of quantum number and quantum mechanics were perceived difficult to learn while the teachers equally found them difficult to teach. Both the teachers and students converged on overloaded curriculum and lack of collaboration and team work as factors accounting for their perceived difficulty. As regards gender effect, non-statistically significant difference existed on the teachers' and students' perception of difficult concepts in the 2020 minimum standard.

The findings underscored the need for targeted interventions, pedagogical strategies, adequate continuing professional development opportunities and training, to address the identified difficulties effectively as well as to enhance teachers' subject knowledge and teaching skills. Furthermore, the study revealed the significance of context-specific teaching approaches tailored to the needs and learning styles of students in colleges of Education in the North West.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

i. Continuing Professional Development: Targeted training and professional development opportunities for chemistry teachers to enhance their subject knowledge and teaching skills should be provided in our Colleges. Workshops, seminars, and refresher courses focusing on effective instructional strategies for difficult concepts should be organized on regular basis by the Colleges and or relevant professional bodies and teachers should be supported to attend.

ii. Minimum Standard review and Teachers Guide: The periodic review of the Minimum Standard should take cognizance of research findings to ensure alignment with the learning needs and contexts of students in the North West region. The teachers' guide should incorporate relevant local examples, contextualize concepts, and simplify complex topics to facilitate better teaching and students understanding.

iii. Pedagogical Support: Pedagogical support to teachers through the provision of teaching resources, lesson plans, lesson observation as enshrined in the accreditation toolkits should be well monitored by the Quality Assurance Directorate of the Colleges. Also instructional materials specifically designed to address difficult chemistry concepts, use of multimedia, hands-on activities, and real-life applications to make learning more engaging, accessible and students-centred should be entrenched in the Colleges.

iv. Digital Chemistry Contents. Teachers should develop online digital chemistry contents with local examples. It is hoped that the students will relate better with such online digital contents than those developed by teachers from other climes.

v. Assessment Practices: In assessing learning achievement, it should be ensured that the assessment practices align with the learning objectives and difficulty levels of chemistry concepts outlined in the Minimum Standard. Furthermore, a variety of assessment methods, including formative assessments, quizzes, and practical demonstrations should be adopted to accurately gauge student understanding and progress.

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vi. Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: The Directorate of Quality Assurance which among others has the role of monitoring curriculum implementation should monitor and evaluate teaching and learning processes to identify areas for improvement and measure the effectiveness of implemented interventions.

It is the considered view of the authors that by implementing these recommendations challenges associated with difficult chemistry concepts in the 2020 Minimum Standard can be addressed, ultimately enhancing the quality of chemistry education in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria and fostering greater students' success and engagement in the subject.

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